

Validation of Single-Phase Fluid Dynamics in a Lattice Boltzmann Simulated JLR

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Keywords

Jet loop reactor, Lattice Boltzmann Method, fluid dynamics, computational flow dynamics, experimental data, simulation and validation

Abstract

Jet loop reactors (JLRs) offer outstanding mixing and heat-transfer performance, but their strongly coupled internal–external circulation makes hydrodynamic design non-trivial. Conventional finite-volume Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) remains computationally demanding, limiting routine optimisation. This study presents the first validated Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) simulation of a single-phase, top-nozzle JLR at industrially relevant specific power inputs of 2.24–5.83 kW m⁻³. The flow was resolved with a D3Q19-LES scheme and halfway bounce-back walls on a locally refined Cartesian lattice. A physical time span of 20 s was simulated in less than 54 h on a single NVIDIA RTX 4090, demonstrating GPU-friendly scalability.

The simulation reproduced measured radial velocity profiles and internal volume flow rates within experimental uncertainty, with remaining deviation below eight per cent. Error analysis indicates that the quadratic lattice and halfway bounce-back wall model slightly narrow the effective annular cross-section, accelerating loop flow. A complementary simulation with the grid rotated by 45 ° suggests grid orientation may amplify or mitigate this artefact, but the magnitude could not be quantified conclusively and is left for future work.

Despite this limitation, the solver captures key hydrodynamic features, including a fully turbulent jet core and weak sensitivity of circulation to power input. Turnaround time is reduced by approximately two orders of magnitude compared with representative RANS studies. The validated workflow provides a foundation for two-phase extensions targeting gas holdup and interfacial mass transfer, enabling rapid simulation of loop reactors.

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1. Introduction

Jet loop reactors (JLRs) are a versatile class of reactors used in both single-phase and multi-phase systems, with applications spanning the chemical and biotechnological industries [1]. They can be employed for aeration of fermentation processes or for chemical synthesis such as oxidations, hydrogenations, carbonylations or hydroformylations. Their industrial relevance arises from several advantages: highly efficient mixing and heat transfer, the ability to operate without mechanically moving parts in the circulation system [2], and a reactor environment characterized by high turbulence and energy dissipation. These features make JLRs especially suitable for reactions sensitive to micromixing and mesomixing effects [3], and macromixing.

A typical Jet loop reactor consists of a cylindrical reactor vessel, a draft tube (DT), and a baffle plate (BP). The central feature of the JLR is the internally circulating flow, driven by a high-velocity jet stream introduced via a nozzle (N). Depending on the reactor design, this nozzle can be positioned either at the top or bottom of the reactor, in the present study it is mounted at the top. The fluid accelerated by the jet travels through the draft tube, is deflected by the baffle plate (forming the bottom redirection zone, BR), and returns through the annular gap (AG) to the head redirection zone (HR), thus completing the internal circulation loop. External recycle is established by pumping fluid from below the baffle plate (bottom space, BS) back to the nozzle. The relative proportions of internal and external circulation are strongly influenced by reactor geometry, particularly the dimensions of the draft tube. Multiple design variants of JLRs exist. As discussed by Schlüter [4] and Reschetilowski [5], these variants primarily differ in nozzle placement (top vs. bottom) and gas injection strategies.

The internal circulation flow of the continuous liquid phase is crucial for the JLR's performance. It influences the macromixing in the reactor i.e., the internal concentration and temperature profiles, which directly affects the conversion of reactants and selectivity to target products. Furthermore, the circulation flow rate determines the stability of circulation in the JLR during multiphase operation, i.e., the entrainment of gas bubbles or solid particles. Additionally, mesomixing in the vicinity of feed points is influenced by circulation flow. Therefore, accurate modeling of the internal circulation flow is essential for JLR design and optimization. Simplified one-dimensional models based on momentum balances and empirical friction correlations offer computationally efficient solutions. These models, calibrated against experimental data, can predict circulation flow rates for specific reactor configurations and operating conditions [6–8]. Recently, we showed that a good agreement between model prediction and experimental results is achieved in a wide parameter range [9]. However, their applicability is limited to geometries for which the empirical correlations have been validated. Design modifications, such as changes to the baffle plate, draft tubes, or structural components, as described in [10], are typically beyond the predictive scope of such models.

In contrast, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) methods offer more detailed insights into flow behavior. Traditional CFD approaches are based on the Navier-Stokes equations, typically solved using finite volume methods (FVM) with turbulence models such as RANS or LES. However, these simulations can be computationally intensive, especially when used for extensive parametric studies [11]. This work applies the Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) as an alternative to traditional CFD. Unlike continuum-based Navier-Stokes solvers, LBM uses a mesoscopic description of fluid flow, modeling the statistical distribution of particle velocities on a discrete lattice. Its explicit solution scheme and suitability for parallelization makes it particularly efficient on GPU architectures [12–14]. This computational efficiency enables faster simulations [15, 16], which is advantageous for iterative reactor design and optimization. LBM, coupled with large eddy simulation (LES) for turbulence modeling, has shown promise in chemical process applications such as stirred tank simulations [17]. Despite their industrial relevance, no peer-reviewed study has yet demonstrated a validated Lattice Boltzmann simulation for the characteristic internal and external loop flow of JLRs, leaving a methodological gap in reactor-scale CFD.

The present work fills the identified gap by coupling a GPU-accelerated D3Q19 LBM-LES solver with laboratory validation data from a top-nozzle JLR operated in single-phase mode. We quantify accuracy, runtime and mesh-induced wall effects, thereby establishing LBM as a viable fast-turnaround design tool for loop reactors and, by extension, other circulation driven process equipment. The commercial software M-Star CFD (version 3.10.118, M-Star Simulations, LLC) is used to conduct the simulations. The validation is carried out by comparing simulated velocity profiles in the annular gap with experimental data. The experimental setup is considered reliable for single-phase validation purposes. Good agreement between simulation and experiment is observed, with all simulated values falling within the measurement uncertainty range. A more detailed analysis reveals that geometric representation errors especially in rounded areas can occur due to the equidistant mesh used in the simulation. Combined with the halfway bounce-back wall model, these errors result in a slight underestimation of the cross-sectional flow area, which must be accounted for in interpretation and future refinement.

Overall, the present Lattice Boltzmann variant is well suited for rapid exploration of a wide range of operating parameters and geometric variations. However, its predictive accuracy is ultimately limited by geometric discretization effects and the employed boundary treatment, which should be considered when high-precision results are required.

2. Lattice Boltzmann Method

The Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) originates from the kinetic theory of gases [18, 19]. It provides a mesoscopic approach to fluid dynamics, bridging the gap between microscopic particle interactions and macroscopic continuum behavior. Through the Chapman-Enskog expansion, the LBM can be shown to recover macroscopic equations such as the Navier-Stokes equations [20, 21].

At its core, the method is based on the Boltzmann equation, which describes the time evolution of the velocity distribution function $f(\vec{x}, \vec{\xi}, t)$:

$$f(\vec{x}, \vec{\xi}, t) = \frac{dN}{dV d\vec{\xi}} \quad (2.1)$$

This function defines the number of molecules or particles N found within an infinitesimal phase space volume $dV d\vec{\xi}$, located at position \vec{x} and moving with velocity $\vec{\xi}$.

In the Lattice Boltzmann framework, space is discretized into an equidistant and orthogonal lattice, time progresses in uniform steps, and the continuous velocity space is approximated by a finite set of discrete velocity vectors. Various lattice models exist for this purpose; in the present work, the D3Q19 model is employed, which represents a three-dimensional grid with 19 discrete velocity directions, as shown in Fig. 2.1.

Figure 2.1.: Illustration of the D3Q19 lattice [22].

The discrete velocity directions $\vec{\xi}_i$ are chosen such that particles travel from one lattice node to a neighboring node within a single time step Δt . The Lattice Boltzmann algorithm consists

of two primary steps [23]. The streaming step and the collision step. In the streaming step, particles propagate along their respective discrete velocity directions $\vec{\xi}_i$ to neighboring nodes. In the collision step, the distribution functions f_i at each node relax toward a local equilibrium state f_i^{eq} , which represents a statistical steady state of the fluid at that location.

Using the Bhatnagar–Gross–Krook approximation [24], the discrete Lattice Boltzmann equation can be written as [25]:

$$f_i(\vec{x} + \xi_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = f_i(\vec{x}, t) + \Omega[f_i^{\text{eq}}(\vec{x}, t) - f_i(\vec{x}, t)] \quad (2.2)$$

Here, f_i is the discrete particle distribution function in the i -th velocity direction, and Ω is the dimensionless collision operator that governs the relaxation process. In the Bhatnagar–Gross–Krook model, Ω is defined as:

$$\Omega = \frac{c_s^2 \Delta t}{\nu + 0.5c_s^2 \Delta t} \quad (2.3)$$

where c_s is the lattice speed of sound and ν is the kinematic viscosity. Ω directly influences the rate at which the system returns to equilibrium and, consequently, affects the simulated flow properties.

The equilibrium distribution function f_i^{eq} , toward which the collision step relaxes the system, is a discrete second-order approximation of the continuous Maxwell–Boltzmann distribution and is as follows:

$$f_i^{\text{eq}}(\vec{x}, t) = w_i \rho \left\{ 1 + \frac{\vec{\xi}_i \vec{v}}{c_s^2} + \frac{(\vec{\xi}_i \vec{v})^2}{2c_s^4} - \frac{v^2}{2c_s^2} \right\} \quad (2.4)$$

Here, \vec{v} is the macroscopic velocity, ρ is the fluid density, w_i are the weighting factors associated with each discrete velocity direction, and c_s is the model-specific speed of sound. Unlike the physical speed of sound, c_s in LBM is defined based on the lattice geometry and time step as:

$$c_s = \frac{\Delta x}{\sqrt{3}\Delta t} \quad (2.5)$$

This parameter influences several aspects of the simulation: it defines the relationship between pressure and density, contributes to the effective viscosity, limits the maximum admissible flow velocity, and ensures the validity of the incompressible flow approximation [19, 26].

For wall modeling, the half-way bounce-back scheme is applied. In this approach, particles striking a wall reverse their momentum direction within a single time step, effectively reflecting back into the fluid domain (see Fig. 2.2). The wall is represented as lying geometrically between a fluid node x_f and a wall node x_w . In the simulation software used in this work, these nodes are positioned such that the simulated cross-sectional area is consistently slightly smaller than the actual physical geometry. This method enforces a no-slip boundary condition but can introduce geometric inaccuracies, especially at inclined or curved surfaces [27].

Figure 2.2.: Illustration of the half-way bounce-back model [22].

In the present work, turbulence is modeled using the Large Eddy Simulation (LES) approach. To account for the influence of unresolved, small-scale vortices on the main flow, a sub-grid-scale viscosity ν_{sgs} is added to the molecular viscosity ν . As a result, the relaxation parameter Ω in the Lattice Boltzmann equation is modified to include both contributions:

$$\Omega = \frac{c_s^2 \Delta t}{\nu + \nu_{\text{sgs}} + 0.5c_s^2 \Delta t} \quad (2.6)$$

The sub-grid-scale viscosity is calculated using the Smagorinsky model [28], which was originally developed for LES modeling of the Navier-Stokes equations [29]. For additional information regarding the implementation and theory, see [14].

Although the Lattice Boltzmann Method traditionally employs uniform, rectangular grids, local grid refinement can be used to enhance accuracy in regions with strong gradients, such as boundary layers, jets, or vortex structures, without significantly increasing computational cost. In this refinement approach, both the grid spacing and the time step are halved at each refinement level to maintain a constant numerical speed of sound across all levels. As a consequence, within a first-order refinement (i.e., level II), the algorithm performs two time steps for every single time step in the coarser base grid.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Experiments

3.1.1. Setup

All investigations in this study were conducted using an upright, laboratory-scale jet loop reactor, operating in a single-phase liquid regime. The same experimental setup was used by Weibel et al. [9]. The circulation within the reactor was induced by a jet nozzle positioned at the reactor head, through which liquid was introduced at high velocity. An overview of the reactor design and configuration is provided in Fig.3.1, which illustrates geometric parameters of the JLR. The associated design parameters are comprehensively listed in Tab. A.1 of the appendix. All components of the reactor were manufactured from transparent acrylic glass, enabling full optical access for flow visualisation and measurement.

The cylindrical reactor had an overall height of $h_R = 1640$ mm and an inner diameter of $d_R = 165$ mm. The central draft tube had a length of $h_{DT} = 1200$ mm and an inner diameter of $d_{DT} = 100$ mm, which corresponds to a ratio of draft tube diameter to reactor diameter of $d_{DT}/d_R = 0.606$.

The nozzle responsible for generating the jet stream had a fixed inlet diameter of 36 mm and a conical shape with a constant angle of 30° . The diameter of the nozzle outlet was $d_N = 12$ mm. The jet was produced by a centrifugal pump, which supplied the external liquid recycle. This pump withdrew liquid from the bottom space (BS) of the reactor and reintroduced it into the headspace (HS) through the nozzle.

Thermal conditions were controlled using a heat exchanger coil located below the baffle plate within the bottom space of the reactor. A cryostat supplied the coolant. Temperature control ensured constant isothermal operation across all experiments.

Detailed information on the instrumentation, including the magnetic-inductive flow meter and impeller anemometer used for hydrodynamic measurements, is provided in Tab. A.2 and the P&I flow diagram in Fig. A.1.

Figure 3.1.: Illustration with the nomenclature of the geometric parameters of the JLR on a laboratory scale.

3.1.2. Measurement Techniques

Fig. A.1 and Tab. A.2 provide an overview of the installed measuring instruments and their respective positions within the reactor system. The volumetric flow rate of the external recycle, $\dot{V}_{I,ER}$, was determined by direct measurement using a magnetic-inductive flow meter. This device requires a minimum electrical conductivity of $20 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$. To ensure reliable measurements under constant conditions, the electrical conductivity of the working fluid was adjusted with sodium chloride to $30 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ using a calibrated conductivity meter.

The internal volume flow rate in the annular gap, $\dot{V}_{I,AG}$, was derived from local velocity measurements performed with an impeller anemometer. The impeller sensor has a diameter of 10 mm and was positioned at the axial center of the reactor, corresponding to the midpoint of the draft tube (see MP in Fig. 3.1). To capture the radial velocity distribution, measurements were taken at eight equidistant radial positions ranging from $r = 77.5 \text{ mm}$ to $r = 60.0 \text{ mm}$ in 2.5 mm increments. The inner limit of the measurement range was constrained by the outer wall of the draft tube, while the outer limit was defined by the reactor wall and the spatial extent of the sensor head.

Temperature within the reactor was measured using a PT100 resistance thermometer located in the bottom space. Temperature control was achieved via an external heat exchanger coil, which was supplied by a cryostat, enabling isothermal operation across all experiments.

3.1.3. Characteristic Performance Indicators

The specific power input φ , and the circulation number N_{circ} , were selected as the principal performance indicators for evaluating the hydrodynamic behavior of the reactor system under various operating conditions. The dimensionless circulation number characterizes the intensity of internal recirculation and serves as a key indicator for evaluating hydrodynamic performance and backmixing phenomena in jet loop reactors, as further described in [9].

The specific power input φ is defined as the kinetic energy per time introduced into the reactor via the jet, normalized by the volume of the reaction zone V_{RZ} between the nozzle outlet and the baffle plate. The volume flow rate of the external recycle $\dot{V}_{\text{I,ER}}$, is equivalent to the volumetric flow through the nozzle, since all liquid circulating through the external loop is reintroduced via the nozzle. The cross-sectional area of the nozzle is denoted by A_{N} . Based on this, the specific power input is calculated according to the following relation:

$$\varphi = \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{I,ER}}^3}{A_{\text{N}}^2 V_{\text{RZ}}} \quad (3.1)$$

Here, ρ denotes the fluid density. The kinetic energy is determined from the measured external recycle flow rate and the exit velocity at the nozzle, which is computed from the nozzle diameter under the assumption of incompressible and steady-state flow.

The circulation number N_{circ} , quantifies the ratio between the internal circulation flow and the external recycle flow. The internal volumetric flow rate through the annular gap $\dot{V}_{\text{I,AG}}$, was obtained by integrating the locally measured axial velocity over the cross-sectional area of the annular gap. Linear interpolation was applied between the individual radial measurement points. At the inner and outer boundaries, the walls of the draft tube and reactor vessel, respectively a no-slip condition was assumed, implying zero velocity at the wall. The circulation number is thus defined as:

$$N_{\text{circ}} = \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{I,AG}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{I,ER}}} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\dot{V}_{\text{I,AG}} = \int_{r_{\text{min}}}^{r_{\text{max}}} v_{\text{AG}}(r) 2\pi r dr \quad (3.3)$$

3.1.4. Experimental Procedure

Initially, the reactor was filled with deionized water from an in-house reverse osmosis system. The conductivity of the water was approximately $0.1 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. To ensure proper functioning of the magnetic-inductive flow meter and to maintain consistent operating conditions, the electrical conductivity of the liquid was adjusted to $30 \pm 2 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ by the addition of sodium chloride, as described in Section 3.1.2. The temperature of the liquid was controlled throughout the entire experimental campaign using a cryostat (see Tab. A.2), enabling operation at a constant temperature of $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

The experimental campaign encompassed three levels of specific power input φ : 2.243 kW m^{-3} , 4.038 kW m^{-3} , and 5.833 kW m^{-3} . These correspond to volume flow rates of the external recycle of $\dot{V}_{1,ER} = 1.175 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $1.429 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, and $1.616 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. For each of the three specific power inputs, eight radial measurement positions in the Annular Gap were investigated, resulting in a total of 24 experimental runs.

For each variation in the specific power input φ , a setpoint was specified and approached by adjusting the volumetric flow rate of the external liquid recycle $\dot{V}_{1,ER}$. The actual specific power input was determined from the measured operating conditions and deviated only slightly from the setpoint, with a maximum deviation of 6.24 % and a substantially lower average deviation. The exact values are provided in the appendix in Tab. A.4.

Prior to each experimental run, the reactor was allowed to reach steady-state operation for at least 60 s. Each experimental run was carried out over a duration of 60 seconds, during which 480 individual measurement values were recorded.

Data acquisition was performed using a central data recorder (see Details in Tab. A.2), which was configured to record eight data points per second from all connected sensors. For each experimental run, the time-resolved data were averaged over the entire recording interval, and the resulting mean values were used in the subsequent analysis and figures.

3.1.5. Quality of the Measurements

The quality of the measurement results was assessed by applying Gaussian error propagation to the derived quantities that are based on direct measurements. This approach was specifically employed to determine the uncertainty in the calculated volume flow rate in the annular gap $\dot{V}_{1,AG}$, and the circulation number N_{circ} . Both quantities are computed from the measured velocity $v_{1,AG}$ and the externally recycled volume flow rate $\dot{V}_{1,ER}$, as defined in Eq. (3.2) and Eq. (3.3). The corresponding combined standard uncertainties were calculated using the general formulation for error propagation in functions of multiple variables.

$$u(y) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_1} u(x_1)\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_2} u(x_2)\right)^2 + \dots} \quad (3.4)$$

For the circulation number N_{circ} and the volume flow rate $\dot{V}_{1,AG}$, the specific expressions for the propagated uncertainties are provided in the appendix, Eq. (A.1) to Eq. (A.3). The uncertainties of the primary measurement devices—namely the magnetic inductive flow meter and the impeller anemometer were adopted from the manufacturer specifications listed in Tab. A.3. No further statistical evaluation of measurement variability was performed, as each operating point was recorded only once. Instead, each result represents the mean of 480 data points acquired over a 60-second interval, which effectively smooths out short-term fluctuations arising from turbulent flow phenomena.

3.2. Simulation Method

3.2.1. Soft- and Hardware

The CAD model was designed using Autodesk Inventor Professional 2025 and exported in STEP format. Meshing and the definition of simulation parameters were carried out in M-Star Pre (version 3.10.118) by M-Star Simulations, LLC. The numerical calculations were performed using M-Star Solve on a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090 GPU. For post-processing and visualization of the simulation results, ParaView version 5.13.2 was used.

3.2.2. Mesh

The CAD model is available in the appendix (see Fig. A.2). Fig. 3.2 shows the schematic illustration of the mesh in the upper part of the reactor.

Figure 3.2.: Schematic illustration of the areas with different spatial resolutions. Area I with 1.5 mm and area II with 0.75 mm.

The total number of lattice nodes in the simulation was 23.4 million, with 13.9 million nodes with a spatial resolution of 1.5 mm (level I) and 9.5 million with a spatial resolution of 0.75 mm (level II), as illustrated in Figure 3.2. The first-order refinement (level II) with a length of 400 mm was applied in the inlet region of the draft tube to more accurately resolve the flow characteristics in this critical area. The original reactor design includes a significantly larger head space. However,

since this region is assumed to have a negligible influence on the overall fluid dynamics due to very low velocities and in order to reduce the number of computational cells the head space was shortened by 54 mm in the simulation model.

3.2.3. Initial and Boundary Values

The simulation began with a quiescent fluid, meaning no initial velocity was present. The initial fluid density was set to $\rho_0 = 1000 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, and the initial pressure was defined as $p_0 = 1013 \text{ mbar}$, representing standard atmospheric pressure. In a single-phase lattice Boltzmann simulation, both density and pressure serve merely as scaling factors and do not directly influence the flow behavior. The walls were modeled using the halfway bounce-back approach, as described in Section 2, which inherently enforces a no-slip boundary condition.

At the inlet, a default volumetric flow rate of $\dot{V}_{\text{in}} = 1.429 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ was prescribed, corresponding to a specific power input of $\varphi = 4.038 \text{ kW m}^{-3}$. This inlet flow rate \dot{V}_{in} corresponds to the experimental volume flow rate of the external recycle $\dot{V}_{\text{l,ER}}$. However, in the simulation, the external recycle loop was not explicitly modeled. Instead, the inlet volumetric flow was directly imposed at the inlet boundary. Thereby the inlet velocity was applied without any profile development; it was uniformly distributed across the entire inlet cross-section, meaning that no velocity gradient or profile flow was present. A ramp-up time of one second was applied to gradually introduce the flow.

For an additional parameter study, the power input was varied to $\varphi = 2.243 \text{ kW m}^{-3}$ and $\varphi = 5.833 \text{ kW m}^{-3}$, corresponding to volumetric flow rates of $\dot{V}_{\text{in}} = 1.175 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\dot{V}_{\text{in}} = 1.616 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. These variations were implemented in accordance with the experimental procedure. The outlet pressure was set to $p_{\text{out}} = 1013 \text{ mbar}$, representing atmospheric conditions. The exact implementation of these boundary conditions in M-Star is not publicly documented. It remains unclear whether the velocity field is imposed through the equilibrium distribution function or through alternative approaches, such as deriving the non-equilibrium component from velocity gradients.

3.2.4. Parameter

A single-phase model with Newtonian rheology was employed for the simulation. To approximate the experimental conditions, the kinematic viscosity of water was set to $\nu = 1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The simulation utilized a D3Q19 lattice configuration combined with a large eddy simulation (LES) turbulence model. Although the use of an implicit LES model is recommended for higher refinement levels, the Smagorinsky LES model was applied here with a coefficient of $C_s = 0.1$.

The spatial resolution was set to $\Delta x = 1.5 \text{ mm}$, providing adequate detail while keeping the cell count within GPU memory limits. For this grid, the lattice speed determines the permissible time step (see Eq. (2.5)). A value of $\Delta t = 4 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}$ was selected, because it keeps the lattice Mach number below 0.3, which preserves the incompressible flow assumption [22]. With these settings, 20 s of physical time were simulated in under 54 h of wall-clock time, striking a practical

balance between numerical accuracy and computational cost. All time-averaged results presented here were computed over the interval $t = 5 - 20$ s.

The error analysis of the numerical simulation cannot be directly quantified, as quantifying the error is beyond the scope of this work. The errors are anticipated to be small. However, the simulations are subject to assumptions and approximations.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Flow Field in the JLR

Fig. 4.1 shows the instantaneous and time-averaged axial velocity fields at a specific power input of $\varphi = 4.038 \text{ kW m}^{-3}$.

Figure 4.1.: Instantaneous axial turbulent velocity field (left) and time-averaged velocity field (right) in the area of the nozzle (top), at the level of the measuring position (center) and the lower redirection zone (bottom) at $t = 20$ s and a specific power input of $\varphi = 4.038 \text{ kW m}^{-3}$.

The time-averaged flow field corresponds well with expectations: a directional pipe flow forms within the draft tube, while a consistent upward flow develops in the annular gap between the draft tube and the reactor wall. In the core region of the reactor, the flow is fully turbulent, as shown in Fig. 4.1, with the highest turbulence intensities occurring in the nozzle jet and at the inlet to the draft tube. These findings align closely with experimentally observed flow patterns. The high inlet velocity of $v_{\text{in}} = 12.6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ leads to strong turbulence in the upper region of the draft tube, which in turn generates significant energy dissipation. This contributes to the reactor's efficient mixing performance.

In contrast to the more structured flow in the lower draft tube and the upper annular gap, the upper and lower redirection zones exhibit pronounced turbulence and strong backmixing. In the

time-averaged flow field, a clear flow separation can be observed at the upper edge of the draft tube during the flow redirection. This separation contributes significantly to frictional losses within the system. Similar flow behavior was already described by Blenke et al. [30]. Moreover, a recent patent suggests a geometric optimization in this region aimed at reducing flow separation and the associated energy losses [10].

In the annular gap, additional flow phenomena are observed due to the cross-sectional constrictions formed by the internal support structures, referred to here as draft tube mount points. These structures induce a flow acceleration upstream of the constrictions and a subsequent stall region directly downstream. These local disturbances influence both pressure losses and mixing behavior in the surrounding flow field.

4.2. Velocity Profiles

Fig. 4.2 shows the radial instantaneous velocity field (left) and the time-averaged velocity field (right) at the same height h_{MP} as the experimental measurement point, which is approximately at the vertical center of the draft tube. This region is selected because the flow is expected to be as undisturbed as possible, minimally affected by the upper and lower deflection zones.

Figure 4.2.: Instantaneous radial turbulent velocity field (left) and time-averaged velocity field (right) at the height of the measuring position h_{MP} at $t = 20$ s and a specific power input of $\varphi = 4.038 \text{ kW m}^{-3}$.

The time-averaged velocity profiles in the annular gap are found to be nearly rotationally sym-

metrical, as further analyzed in the appendix (see Section A.4). This symmetry confirms the consistency of the simulation setup and the physical plausibility of the results.

Against this background, the following Fig. 4.3 presents the velocity profile as a function of the radius at a selected angle corresponding to the measurement location of the experiment, which has an angular offset of 45° compared to the draft tube support structures (compare Fig. A.2). This profile is then compared with experimental data.

Figure 4.3.: Time-averaged velocity component in the annular gap $\bar{v}_{z,AG}$ at the height of the measuring position h_{MP} as a function of the radial position r for experimental (symbol) and simulation data (line) for different specific power inputs φ .

Both in the experiment and in the simulation, the velocity of the core flow decreases with increasing radial distance from the reactor center. Toward the reactor walls, the simulated velocity profile approaches zero, which is consistent with the widely accepted assumption of a no-slip boundary condition at solid walls. In contrast, the experimentally measured velocity profiles do not exhibit this behavior as clearly – a deviation that can be attributed to limitations in the measurement technique. The measuring points are 2.5 mm apart, while the impeller anemometer has a diameter of 10 mm. As a result, the vane wheel covers four to five measuring points simultaneously, which leads to a reduction in measuring accuracy. Inaccuracies in the measurement occur particularly in the peripheral areas, as the water does not flow freely around the anemometer. Furthermore, it is an invasive measuring method in which the measuring device itself influences the flow.

We also examined the cross-sectional area and found that M-Star reports a smaller area than the actual one. This would lead to an increase in the simulated velocity. This discrepancy is likely due to the half-way bounce-back model as implemented in M-Star, especially velocity profiles along grid diagonals. This phenomenon is further discussed in Section A.4. Nevertheless, the absolute velocity values from the simulation match the experimental data closely and lie within both the angle-dependent simulation uncertainties and the measurement uncertainties.

Assuming that the experimentally determined velocities at the edges decrease linearly to zero and that the measurement points are connected using linear interpolation, the experimental volumetric flow rate in the annular gap, respectively the circulation number was calculated using

Eq. 3.2 and compared between the simulation and the experimental results for the different specific power inputs. Tab. 4.1 summarizes the results.

Table 4.1.: Time-averaged circulation number in the simulation $\overline{N}_{\text{circ,sim}}$ and in the experiment $\overline{N}_{\text{circ,exp}}$ for different specific power inputs φ .

$\varphi/\text{kW m}^{-3}$	$\overline{N}_{\text{circ,sim}}$	$\overline{N}_{\text{circ,exp}}$
2.243	3.07	3.25 ± 0.47
4.038	3.18	3.42 ± 0.41
5.833	3.16	3.38 ± 0.37

It can be seen in Tab. 4.1 that the specific power input has little effect on the circulation number, both experimentally and in the simulation. This is consistent with the literature [5] and one-dimensional models [8, 9].

Assuming that the experimental velocity at 45° , halfway between the support structures, is slightly overestimated as indicated by the simulation in Fig. A.3 and Section A.4, the experimental circulation number is likewise overestimated. This occurs because its calculation treats the velocity as constant over the whole angle, whereas the simulated circulation number is derived from the volumetric flow through the entire annular gap.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

This study demonstrates, for the first time to the authors' knowledge, the successful application of the Lattice Boltzmann Method to a jet loop reactor. Compared with conventional CFD approaches such as RANS, the LBM workflow reduced wall-clock time substantially while still reproducing the essential hydrodynamic features of the apparatus over a physical time span of twenty seconds. The method therefore appears well suited to the class of JLRs that are of particular interest in process engineering. Quantitatively, the time-averaged radial velocity profiles in the annular gap agreed with experimental data to within the uncertainty band imposed by the invasive vane-anemometer technique. The principal numerical shortcoming was traced to the half-way bounce-back wall model, which slightly shrinks the effective cross-section and thereby over-predicts near-wall velocities.

Taken together, the present results establish LBM as a fast and reliable simulation platform for JLRs and provide a solid foundation for both geometric optimisation and multiphase extensions in future studies. Although the JLR was used here as a representative case, the approach is readily applicable to other process-engineering reactors that feature strong jets, recirculation zones, or complex internal geometries. In this sense, the JLR serves as a model system for demonstrating the capabilities of LBM rather than as a unique or isolated example.

One possible approach to improve the simulation results is to use of more advanced wall models, such as the wall model proposed by Bouzidi [31]. Future work could aim to extend the solver to a two-phase framework, which would open the door to predicting gas holdup and interfacial mass-transfer coefficients. Parallel experimental work should employ non-invasive diagnostics such as Particle Image Velocimetry to obtain undisturbed, two-dimensional velocity fields for stricter validation.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to Johannes Wutz (M-Star Simulations, LLC) for his valuable support and contributions to this project. His assistance and expertise were greatly appreciated and helped to advance the work presented in this paper

References

- [1] H. Warmeling, A. Behr, and A. J. Vorholt, “Jet loop reactors as a versatile reactor set up - intensifying catalytic reactions: A review,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 149, pp. 229–248, 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2016.04.032
- [2] S. Weber, S. Schaepe, S. Freyer, M.-H. Kopf, and C. Dietzsch, “Effect of ejector operation on the oxygen transfer in a pilot jet loop reactor,” *Chemical Engineering and Processing - Process Intensification*, vol. 131, pp. 43–50, 2018. DOI: 10.1016/j.cep.2018.07.007
- [3] J. R. Bourne, “Mixing and the selectivity of chemical reactions,” *Organic Process Research & Development*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 471–508, 2003. DOI: 10.1021/op020074q
- [4] Schlüter, Michael and Warnecke, Hans-Joachim and Zehner, Peter, “Reaktoren für fluid-fluid-reaktionen: Schlaufenreaktoren,” in *Handbuch Chemische Reaktoren: Grundlagen und Anwendungen der Chemischen Reaktionstechnik*, W. Reschetilowski, Ed., Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2019, pp. 1–32, ISBN: 978-3-662-56444-8. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-56444-8{\textunderscore}28-1
- [5] W. Reschetilowski, *Handbuch Chemische Reaktoren*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2020, ISBN: 978-3-662-56433-2. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-56434-9
- [6] O. Bey and E. von Harbou, “Einfluss der wechselwirkung von reaktion und fluiddynamik auf das verhalten von strahlschlaufenreaktoren,” *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 93, no. 1-2, pp. 191–200, 2021. DOI: 10.1002/cite.202000156
- [7] P. Zehner and Verein Deutscher Ingenieure, *Flüssigkeits/Feststoff-Strömungen in verfahrenstechnischen Apparaten* (Fortschritt-Berichte VDI. Reihe 3, Verfahrenstechnik). VDI Verlag, 1988. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.de/books?id=HzdzzwEACAAJ>
- [8] F. Breit, O. Bey, and E. von Harbou, “Model-based investigation of the interaction of gas-consuming reactions and internal circulation flow within jet loop reactors,” *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 7, p. 1297, 2022. DOI: 10.3390/pr10071297
- [9] C. Weibel, F. Breit, T. Melchior, and E. von Harbou, *Predictive modeling and experimental validation of internal circulation in single phase jet loop reactors*, 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17775734
- [10] R. D. Loeffler, A. Woelfert, E. J. von Harbou, and B. Brunner, “Internal loop reactor,” US 2025/0033020 A1, 30.01.2025.
- [11] X. Zhang et al., “Physics-informed data-driven unsteady reynolds-averaged navier–stokes turbulence modeling for particle-laden jet flows,” *Physics of Fluids*, vol. 36, no. 5, p. 053 325, 2024. DOI: 10.1063/5.0206090

- [12] J. Tölke, “Implementation of a lattice boltzmann kernel using the compute unified device architecture developed by nvidia,” *Computing and Visualization in Science*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 29–39, 2010. DOI: 10.1007/s00791-008-0120-2
- [13] C. Obrecht, F. Kuznik, B. Tourancheau, and J.-J. Roux, “Multi-gpu implementation of the lattice boltzmann method,” *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 252–261, 2013. DOI: 10.1016/j.camwa.2011.02.020
- [14] L.-S. Luo, M. Krafczyk, and W. Shyy, “Lattice boltzmann method for computational fluid dynamics,” in 2010, ISBN: 9780470686652. DOI: 10.1002/9780470686652.eae064
- [15] M. T. Rahni, M. Alizadeh, M. Haghshenas, H. Salimi, M. Najafi, and R. Miller, “Applicability of lattice boltzmann method in simulation of drops and bubbles formation and transport,” ser. AIP Conference Proceedings, AIP Publishing LLC, 2015, p. 790 002. DOI: 10.1063/1.4912998
- [16] M. L. Hosain and R. B. Fdhila, “Literature review of accelerated cfd simulation methods towards online application,” *Energy Procedia*, vol. 75, pp. 3307–3314, 2015. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2015.07.714
- [17] J. Kersebaum, S. Flaischlen, J. Hofinger, and G. D. Wehinger, “Simulating stirred tank reactor characteristics with a lattice boltzmann cfd code,” *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 586–595, 2024. DOI: 10.1002/ceat.202300384
- [18] U. Frisch, B. Hasslacher, and and Y. Pomeau, “Lattice-gas automata for the navier-stokes equation,” vol. 56, no. 14, pp. 1505–1508, 1986. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.56.1505
- [19] R. Benzi, S. Succi, and M. Vergassola, “The lattice boltzmann equation: Theory and applications,” *Physics Reports*, vol. 222, no. 3, pp. 145–197, 1992. DOI: 10.1016/0370-1573(92)90090-M [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/037015739290090M>
- [20] D. Hänel, *Molekulare Gasdynamik: Einführung in die kinetische Theorie der Gase und Lattice-Boltzmann-Methoden*. 2004, ISBN: 978-3-540-44247-9. DOI: 10.1007/3-540-35047-0
- [21] D.V. Patil, “Chapman–enskog analysis for finite-volume formulation of lattice boltzmann equation,” *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, vol. 392, no. 12, pp. 2701–2712, 2013. DOI: 10.1016/j.physa.2013.02.016 [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S037843711300174X>
- [22] A. Schneider, “A consistent large eddy approach for lattice boltzmann methods and its application to complex flows,” Doctoralthesis, Technische Universität Kaiserslautern, 2015.
- [23] Y. Chen and Q. Cai, “The lattice boltzmann method based on quadtree mesh,” *Modern Physics Letters B - MOD PHYS LETT B*, vol. 23, pp. 289–292, 2009. DOI: 10.1142/S0217984909018229
- [24] Y. H. Qian, D. D’Humières, and P. Lallemand, “Lattice bgk models for navier-stokes equation,” *Europhysics Letters*, vol. 17, no. 6, p. 479, 1992. DOI: 10.1209/0295-5075/17/6/001

- [25] Xiaoyi He, Shiyi Chen, and Gary D. Doolen, “A novel thermal model for the lattice boltzmann method in incompressible limit,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 146, no. 1, pp. 282–300, 1998. DOI: 10.1006/jcph.1998.6057 [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0021999198960570>
- [26] T. Krüger, H. Kusumaatmaja, A. Kuzmin, O. Shardt, G. Silva, and E. M. Viggien, *The Lattice Boltzmann method : principles and practice* (Graduate texts in physics), Soft-cover reprint of the hardcover 1st edition 2016. Cham], Switzerland: Springer, 2017, ISBN: 9783319831039.
- [27] C. Peng, Y. Teng, B. Hwang, Z. Guo, and L.-P. Wang, “Implementation issues and benchmarking of lattice boltzmann method for moving rigid particle simulations in a viscous flow,” *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, vol. 72, no. 2, pp. 349–374, 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.camwa.2015.08.027
- [28] J. SMAGORINSKY, “General circulation experiments with the primitive equations: I. the basic experiment,” *Monthly Weather Review*, vol. 91, no. 3, pp. 99–164, 1963. DOI: 10.1175/1520-0493(1963)091<>0099:GCEWTP<>2.3.CO;2 [Online]. Available: https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/mwre/91/3/1520-0493_1963_091_0099_gcewtp_2_3_co_2.xml
- [29] Jiri Blazek, “Chapter 7 - turbulence modeling,” in *Computational Fluid Dynamics: Principles and Applications (Third Edition)*, Jiri Blazek, Ed., Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann, 2015, pp. 213–252, ISBN: 978-0-08-099995-1. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-08-099995-1.00007-5 [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780080999951000075>
- [30] H. Blenke, K. Bohner, and W. Pfeiffer, “Hydrodynamische berechnung von schlaufenreaktoren für einphasensysteme,” *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 43, no. 1-2, pp. 10–17, 1971. DOI: 10.1002/cite.330430103
- [31] M. Bouzidi, M. Firdaouss, and P. Lallemand, “Momentum transfer of a boltzmann-lattice fluid with boundaries,” *Physics of Fluids*, vol. 13, no. 11, pp. 3452–3459, 2001. DOI: 10.1063/1.1399290

Nomenclature

Latin letters

A	Cross-sectional area	m^2
c_s	Lattice speed of sound	m s^{-1}
C_s	Smagorinsky coefficient	–
d	Diameter	m
Δr	Radial discretization	m
Δt	Temporal discretization	s
Δx	Spatial discretization	m
f	Velocity distribution function	s^3m^{-6}
f_i	Discrete velocity distribution function	kgm^{-3}
h	Height	m
N	Number of molecules or particles	–
N_{circ}	Circulation number	–
$\overline{N}_{\text{circ}}$	Time-averaged circulation number	–
p	Pressure	Pa
p_0	Initial pressure	Pa
r	Radius	m
s	Thickness	mm
t	Time	s
T	Temperatur	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
u	Uncertainty	–
V	Volume	m^{-3}
v	Fluid velocity	m s^{-1}
\bar{v}	Time-averaged fluid velocity	m s^{-1}
\vec{v}	Fluid velocity vector	m s^{-1}
\dot{V}	Volume flow rate	m^3s^{-1}
w_i	Weighting factor	–
x	Independent input variables	
\vec{x}	Position vector	m
x_f	Position of a fluid node	m
x_w	Position of a wall node	m
$\vec{\xi}_i$	Discrete velocity directions	m s^{-1}
$\vec{\xi}$	Velocity vector	m s^{-1}
y	Variable under consideration	
z	Coordinate in z direction	m

Greek letters

ν	Kinematic viscosity	m^2s^{-1}
ν_{sgs}	Sub-grid-scale viscosity	m^2s^{-1}
Ω	Dimensionless collision operator	–
φ	Specific power input	Wm^{-3}
ρ	Fluid density	kgm^{-3}
ρ_0	Initial density	kgm^{-3}
θ	Angle	$^\circ$

Subscripts

exp	Experiment
in	Inlet
l	Liquid
max	Maximum
min	Minimum
out	Outlet
sim	Simulation

Superscripts

eq	Equilibrium
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Abbreviations

AG	Annular gap
BP	Baffle plate
BR	Bottom redirection
BS	Bottom space
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DT	Draft tube
ER	External recycle
f.F.	Full Scale
FI	Flow indicator
f.M.	from Measured value
FVM	Finite volume methods
GPU	Graphics processing unit
HR	Head redirection
HS	Headspace
JLR	Jet loop reactor
LBM	Lattice Boltzmann Methods

continued ...

... continued

LES	Large Eddy Simulation
MP	Measuring point
N	Nozzle
P	Pump
PI	Pressure indicator
R	Reactor
RANS	Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations
RZ	Reaction zone
SI	Velocity (Speed) indicator
V	Valve

Note if a variable has no unit this is indicated by -, if no specification is made the unit of the variable can change.

A. Appendix

A.1. Detail Experimental Setup

A.1.1. Reactor Geometry and Dimensions

Table A.1.: Reactor geometry and nomenclature of the design parameters.

Description	Parameters	Value / mm
Dimensions		
Reactor height	h_R	1640
Reactor diameter	d_R	165
Design parameters		
Draft tube length	h_{DT}	1200
Draft tube diameter (inside)	d_{DT}	60, 80, 100
Draft tube wall thickness	s_{DT}	5
Nozzle length, Height head space	$h_N = h_{HS}$	73
Nozzle diameter	d_N	6, 8, 10, 12
Height head redirection zone	h_{HR}	95
Baffle plate diameter	d_{BP}	145
Baffle plate thickness	s_{BP}	5
Height bottom redirection zone	h_{BR}	115
Height bottom space	h_{BS}	157
Height reactive zone	h_{RZ}	1408
Measuring positions		
Centered in the annular gap	h_{MP}	920

A.1.2. Measuring equipment

Figure A.1.: P&I - Flow diagram of the JLR laboratory system setup [9].

Table A.2.: List of measuring equipment and devices of the JLR laboratory system.

Symbols	Description	Model – type	Manufacturer
Measuring equipment			
FI1	Flow meter	OPTIFLUX 5000	Krohne (Duisburg, Germany)
SI	Impeller anemometer	MiniAir64 Micro Water	TSR-Messtechnik AG (Schaffhausen, Switzerland)
-	conductivity meter	Seven2Go pro, InLab 742-ISM	Mettler Toledo (Switzerland)
Devices			
	Pump	CME5-6	Grundfos (Erkrath, Germany)
	Cryostat	ECOCOOL 150R	Grant Instruments, (Shepreth, United Kingdom)
	Data recorder	6100A	Eurotherm (Limburg a.d. Lahn, Germany)

A.1.3. Measurement Uncertainty

The calculation of static measurement errors is based on the measurement uncertainties of the manufacturer, as outlined in Tab. A.3.

Table A.3.: Manufacturer information on the measurement uncertainty of the measuring instruments used.

Symbol	Designation	Uncertainty	Measuring range
FI1	Flow meter	$\pm 0.15 \%$	–
SI1	Impeller anemometer	$\pm 1.0 \%$ f.F. + $\pm 3.5 \%$ f.M.	$0.04 - 5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$

The uncertainty of the circulation number according to Gauss can be determined using equation (Eq. (A.1)), which is based on the uncertainty of the measured variables $\dot{V}_{I,ER}$ and $v_{I,AG}$.

$$u(N_{\text{circ}}) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial N_{\text{circ}}}{\partial \dot{V}_{I,ER}} u(\dot{V}_{I,ER})\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial N_{\text{circ}}}{\partial v_{I,AG}} u(v_{I,AG})\right)^2} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

As the volume flow in the annular gap is the result of the velocity integrated over the radius (see equation 3.3), the calculation of the uncertainty is undertaken in accordance with Eq. (A.2).

$$\begin{aligned} u(\dot{V}_{I,AG}(r)) &= \int_{r_{\min}}^{r_{\max}} \frac{\partial \dot{V}_{I,AG}(r)}{\partial v_{AG}(r)} u(v_{AG}(r)) \, dr \\ &= \int_{r_{\min}}^{r_{\max}} (2\pi r) u(v_{AG}(r)) \, dr \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

For discrete measured values, the integral is replaced by a summation.

$$u(\dot{V}_{I,AG}) = \sum_{i=1}^n (2\pi r_i \Delta r) (v_{AG}(r_i)) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

A.2. CAD Model

Fig. A.2 presents the CAD model of the geometry employed in this study. The support ring surrounding the draft tube at the bottom and its associated support structures are visible. Two supports are positioned at the top of the draft tube, diametrically opposed (180° apart), while four supports are located at the bottom, spaced at 90° intervals.

Figure A.2.: CAD representation of the reactor adapted for simulation.

A.3. Measurement data

Table A.4.: Overview of all experimental measurement data.

r mm	$\dot{V}_{I,ER}$ $\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$	φ W m^{-3}	$v_{I,AG}$ m s^{-1}	T $^{\circ}\text{C}$
60.0	4156.3 ± 6.2	2136.9 ± 9.6	0.424	21
62.5	4158.4 ± 6.2	2140.3 ± 9.6	0.421	21
65.0	4134.0 ± 6.2	2102.8 ± 9.5	0.412	21
67.5	4167.5 ± 6.3	2154.2 ± 9.7	0.400	22
70.0	4146.7 ± 6.2	2122.2 ± 9.6	0.395	22
72.5	4182.9 ± 6.3	2178.2 ± 9.8	0.385	22
75.0	4174.8 ± 6.3	2165.5 ± 9.7	0.380	22
77.5	4204.0 ± 6.3	2211.4 ± 10.0	0.351	22
60.0	5158.6 ± 7.7	4085.8 ± 18.4	0.559	21
62.5	5152.9 ± 7.7	4072.1 ± 18.3	0.532	21
65.0	5165.8 ± 7.7	4102.9 ± 18.5	0.526	21
67.5	5141.9 ± 7.7	4046.2 ± 18.2	0.510	21
70.0	5159.0 ± 7.7	4086.6 ± 18.4	0.505	21
72.5	5146.8 ± 7.7	4057.7 ± 18.3	0.487	21
75.0	5171.0 ± 7.8	4115.2 ± 18.5	0.470	21
77.5	5165.5 ± 7.7	4102.1 ± 18.5	0.454	20
60.0	5834.9 ± 8.8	5909.8 ± 26.6	0.613	22
62.5	5849.6 ± 8.8	5954.6 ± 26.8	0.602	22
65.0	5892.0 ± 8.8	6085.2 ± 27.4	0.584	23
67.5	5913.3 ± 8.9	6151.3 ± 27.7	0.569	23
70.0	5853.8 ± 8.8	5967.6 ± 26.9	0.564	23
72.5	5890.1 ± 8.8	6079.4 ± 27.4	0.549	23
75.0	5870.3 ± 8.8	6018.0 ± 27.1	0.538	23
77.5	5864.6 ± 8.8	6000.6 ± 27.0	0.511	24

A.4. Simulation

To evaluate the rotational symmetry Fig. A.3 (left) shows the velocity profiles for different radial angles. Here the draft tube support structures are aligned with the mesh.

Figure A.3.: Time-averaged velocity component in the annular gap $\bar{v}_{z,AG}$ at the height of the measuring position h_{MP} as a function of the radial position r for different radial angles θ with the draft tube support structures aligned to the mesh (left) and rotated 45 degrees (right) at $t = 20$ s and a specific power input of $\varphi = 4.038 \text{ kW m}^{-3}$.

Minor deviations from perfect symmetry can be attributed to two primary factors. First, the presence of four fixed support structures symmetrically mounted at 90° intervals on the outer wall of the draft tube result in a slight increase in velocity in between the structures, not only directly above the structures but also further downstream. This phenomenon explains the slightly increased velocity profiles observed at the angles of 45° and 135° . Second, numerical effects may play a role, particularly because the number of grid points across the radius is lower at angular positions of 45° and 135° , compared to the 0° , 90° , and 180° directions. These numerical effects are due to the equidistant, cube-shaped computational grid employed by the Lattice Boltzmann Method, to which the draft tube support structures are aligned. Additionally, the implemented wall model leads to a reduction in the effective cross-sectional flow area. This artificial constriction is particularly pronounced in regions with fewer lattice nodes across the radius, as is the case at non-orthogonal angles such as 45° and 135° . Furthermore, a constriction of the simulated cross-sectional area leads to an increase in velocity.

Both phenomena were investigated in a further simulation in which the draft tube support structures were rotated 45 degrees to the calculation grid. The velocity profiles are shown in Fig. A.3 (right). The velocity profiles at 45° and 135° are lower when the draft tube is rotated by 45° . In this case, the support structures of the draft tube are also rotated by 45° , placing them at the 45° and 135° positions. This results in a physical reduction in the flow profile upstream of the annular gap, which is reflected in the simulation. On the other hand, the velocity profiles at the 0° , 90° , and 180° positions are higher when the draft tube is rotated by 45° . In this case, these velocity profiles are located upstream of the annular gap, directly between the support structures. However, when examining the velocity profiles from the simulation with the draft tube rotated by 45° , it is noticeable that the velocity profiles at the 0° , 90° , and 180° positions, i.e., between the support structures, are not necessarily higher than the profiles at the 45° and 135° positions, i.e., directly above the support structures. In the simulation without the 45° rotation of the draft tube, the profiles between the support structures are always higher than those at the support structures. This suggests that numerical effects may be at play, especially considering that the number of cells across the radius is lower at the 45° and 135° angles compared to the 0° , 90° , and 180° angles. This is particularly relevant in the context of the wall model used, which consistently results in a

numerical cross-sectional area smaller than the physical one, which increases the simulated velocity. This effect becomes more pronounced as the number of numerical grid points decreases.

In summary, it can be stated that the effect of the increased velocity profiles in the standard simulation at the 45° angle, i.e., between the draft tube support structures, is due to both physical and numerical effects.